

Studies in Ion-exchange Equilibria. Part III. Exchange of Univalent Cations on Amberlite IR-120 in Aqueous Ethanol

R. P. Bhatnagar, R. C. Arora, and K. K. Kurian

Equilibrium studies for exchange of diverse types of univalent cations on a nuclear sulphonic acid type of exchanger, Amberlite IR-120 (H), have been made in aqueous ethanolic solutions. Observations have been made regarding linear increase of percentage of exchange and regular increase of $\log K_a$ with increase in percentage of ethanol. Effect of the quantity of the resin and of presence of an anion on percentage of exchange have also been studied. Irregular variability of K_a with X_{Et} has also been observed in aqueous ethanolic solutions.

Though extensive exchange equilibrium studies have been reported in aqueous solutions^{1-3,14}, there are only few in non-aqueous medium⁴⁻¹³. Most of the studies in non-aqueous media, using synthetic commercially available exchangers, are from the point of view of swelling and exchange capacities.

The recent equilibrium studies include work in anhydrous methanol⁸, aqueous acetone^{9,10,13}, aqueous dioxane¹⁰⁻¹², and in aqueous ethanol¹¹⁻¹². The studies in aqueous ethanol has been performed with Ag^+ either against H^+ or NH_4^+ . Thus it appears that varied types of cations on different types of exchangers have not been studied in this solvent nor they have been studied to investigate the variability of K_a (as shown in an earlier communication⁴) in non-aqueous solvents.

The present studies have been performed on a nuclear sulphonic acid type of highly cross-linked cation exchanger, Amberlite IR-120 (H-form). The alkali metal ions (Li^+ , Na^+ , and K^+) together with univalent ions as Tl^+ and Ag^+ have been studied in aqueous ethanol solutions to bring forth the conclusions regarding variability of extent of exchange, affinity sequences, and equilibrium constant with respect to the concentration of ethanol and quantity of the resin. Effect of anions on the exchange of cations in aqueous ethanolic solvents has also been studied.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The stock solutions of univalent cations were prepared from B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or E. Merck "Extra puris" nitrates of metals concerned. Potassium salts (chloride, bromide, iodide, and nitrate) were used for the study of anion effect. All stock solutions were 0.1*N* and other strengths were prepared by proper dilutions. All ethanolic solutions (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 60%) of different cation concentrations (0.05 *N*, 0.025 *N*, and 0.01 *N*) were prepared by taking the stock solutions and mixing them with absolute ethanol and distilled water in required proportions.

A.R. sample of the hydrogen form of Amberlite IR-120 (Rohm & Haas Co., Philadelphia, U.S.A.) was used for the equilibrium studies which were performed by batch technique.

Procedure.—Always 50 ml of the cation solution (containing various percentages of ethanol) was equilibrated in 250 ml 'Pyrex' Erlenmeyer flasks with 0.5 g. of the air-dry resin for about 24 hours. After equilibration aliquots (10 ml) from lithium, sodium, and potassium solutions were titrated for generated acidity with a standardised NaOH solution to phenolphthalein end point to obtain the amount of exchange of the ion concerned. In cases of thallium(I) and silver exchanges, the amount of exchange at equilibrium was determined by estimating the ions volumetrically in the aliquots by potassium iodate and thiocyanate solution respectively.

For studying the effect of the amount of resin, similar studies were performed on potassium salt solutions with different ethanolic percentages, using 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, and 1.5 g. of the resin.

For anion effect, potassium salt solutions with different ethanol percentages were used with 0.5 g. of the resin. Total volume of the solution was kept at 50 ml in all cases.

The total capacity of the resin was determined as usual by the method of Heyman and O' Donnell¹⁵. The percentage exchange was calculated from the values of m.e. of cations added and exchanged, whereas equilibrium constant (apparent) was calculated according to the method used by Kressman and Kitchener³ and adopted by us in an earlier work⁴.

Graphs were plotted for different ions at 0.05*N*, 0.025*N*, and 0.01*N* solution concentrations for variation of % exchange with ethanol % (v/v) (see Fig. 1, A, B & C). Graphs were also plotted for variation of $\log_{10} K_a$ with percentage of ethanol for all ions concerned (Fig. 2). Graphs of K_a vs. X_{B_2} (Figs. 3 & 4) were also drawn for Na⁺ exchange at different ethanol percentages and such comparative variations in case of all the ions in 30% ethanolic solutions.

Results for the effect of quantity of resin on exchange of K⁺ ion in aqueous ethanolic solutions are recorded in Table I; the effect of anion on percentage of exchange for K⁺ ion is clear from Table II.

TABLE I

*Effect of quantity of resin on the percentage of K⁺-ion exchange.*Conc. of the soln. = $N/40$.

% EtOH.	Exchange (%).			
	Resin (0.5 g.).	Resin (0.75 g.).	Resin (1.0 g.).	Resin (1.5 g.).
0	67.25	61.52	54.28	43.17
10	69.16	65.14	56.99	44.98
20	71.96	68.24	60.49	46.78
30	77.75	71.47	64.36	48.86
40	81.27	75.99	68.24	49.88
60	88.90	83.75	76.18	51.95

TABLE II

*Effect of anions on exchange of K⁺-ion on Amberlite IR-120(H).*Conc. of the soln. = $N/40$.

%EtOH.	Exchange (%).			
	Cl ⁻ .	Br ⁻ .	I ⁻ .	NO ₃ ⁻ .
0	79.10	70.56	62.81	67.25
10	79.10	74.44	65.91	69.16
20	82.97	78.32	69.70	71.96
30	86.83	82.56	81.42	77.75
40	96.73	94.60	83.75	81.27
60	97.71	96.18	93.05	88.90

DISCUSSION

The results of the present studies indicate the following trends in aqueous ethanol solvent mixtures:

1. The exchange sequence for univalent alkali metal ions remains as $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$ in aqueous ethanol solution (same as in aqueous solutions); but the sequence of exchange for Ag^+ changes with increase in percentage of ethanol. Thus for the ions used, the sequence is in the increasing order as: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Ag}^+ < \text{Tl}^+$ in aqueous ethanol solvents containing 0 to 30% EtOH, but at higher percentages of EtOH (40 onwards) Ag^+ shows less affinity for the exchanger than K^+ (or even Na^+ for very high percentages of EtOH). The sequence in solution containing 40% EtOH thus becomes: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Ag}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Tl}^+$.

2. The percentage of exchange increases linearly with %EtOH (v/v) as is clear from graphs in Fig. 1.

3. The percentage exchange also depends on the quantity of the resin (Table I). With increasing quantities of the resin, the percentage of exchange in aqueous or partly aqueous solutions decreases.

FIG. 1. Variation of percentage of exchange with EtOH concentration.

4. The stoichiometric equilibrium constant or apparent equilibrium constant is also dependent on the ethanol concentration of the medium. All other variables being same, it increases regularly with the concentration of EtOH (Fig. 2).

5. The stoichiometric equilibrium constant is not a constant quantity. It varies irregularly with X_{B_2} , the equivalent fraction of the cation in the resin phase after equilibration. (vide Figs. 3 and 4). For any one ion, the maxima in K_a - X_{B_2} plots also change with ethanol concentration (Fig. 3).

6. The percentage of cation exchange also is dependent on the presence of a particular type of anion with it. Thus for metal halides, exchange percentage was more for metal chlorides than metal iodides. Bigger the size of the anion associated with cation, less is the percentage exchange of the cation on a cation exchanger.

The above observations clearly show that presence of a non-aqueous solvent modifies the exchange in some way or the other. The observation that percentage of exchange increases with percentage of EtOH for univalent cations of all types on Amberlite IR-120 is supported by earlier observations of Wiegner⁵⁻⁶, Kressman and Kitchener⁴, and Bafna⁹. Wiegner⁵⁻⁶, using aluminosilicate exchanger, and Kressman and Kitchener⁴, using phenol sulphonate resin in ammonium form, concluded that the above-mentioned variation was linear. The present studies with H-form of the nuclear sulphonic acid type of cation exchanger confirm the findings with added support from the results of varied types of univalent cations. The variation of equilibrium constant with EtOH concentrations is also supported by these earlier workers. Bafna⁹ came to similar conclusions in case of aqueous acetone. The studies of Kressman and Kitchener⁴ were carried out at 0.1*N* and in a few cases at 0.05*N* solutions, whereas those of Bafna⁹ were at *N*/8 concentration. The present studies were carried out in 0.05 *N*, 0.025*N*, and 0.01*N* solutions, showing the validity of the observations in dilute solutions.

FIG. 2. Variation of $\log_{10} K_a$ with EtOH concentration.

The plots of $\log K_a$ vs. %EtOH from Kressman and Kitchener⁴ were straight lines, whereas those of Bafna were initially linear and later on changed to smooth curves of little curvature. Our plots (Fig. 2) are not straight lines, but smooth curves showing a regular increase in the slope, similar in shape to the work of Bafna in acetone.

The effect of the quantity of resin on the extent of exchange, as observed here, is in line with similar observations by Bafna⁹ from studies in aqueous acetone.

As has been shown by many workers¹⁴⁻¹⁷ in aqueous studies, K_a is not a constant quantity in alcoholic solutions too. It varies with X_{B_2} irregularly (Figs. 3 and 4). The variation and the maxima in variation curves depend on several other factors, such as, the ion species, ethanol concentration, etc. This is contrary to the conclusions of

16. Duncan and Lister, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3285.

17. Lowen et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2666.

Kressman and Kitchener⁴ who carried out their studies at a fixed ionic concentration, varying only alcohol concentration.

FIG. 3. K_A variation with X_{Na} at different EtOH concentrations for the exchange of Na^+ .

FIG. 4. K_A variation with X_{Na} at 30% EtOH concentration for univalent ions.

The increase in the extent of exchange and hence in %exchange in non-aqueous solvents has been explained in different ways by different workers. Wiegner⁶ correlated this change with dielectric constant of the mixture which similarly varied with the concentration of ethanol. Kressman and Kitchener⁴ though initially believed in Wiegner's concept but later on raised doubts about it. They suggested that a° values, which changes to different extents in different alcoholic solutions, is responsible for differences in stoichiometric exchange equilibrium values. Gregor¹⁸ and also Reichenberg¹⁹ suggested that ion exchangers may be modelled as a swelled gel. The equilibrium is attained in it when the swelling pressure balances the elastic restraint (which in effect is similar to normal external pressure on an osmotic system). They deduced the equation

$$RT \ln K_A^B = p(\bar{V}_A - \bar{V}_B)$$

(where K_A^B is the relative affinity coefficient; p , the swelling pressure at equilibrium; $\bar{V}_A$ and $\bar{V}_B$ are the partial molal volumes of the hydrated cations in the resin).

An alternative approach of Glueckauf²⁰ and Duncan²¹ did not emphasise on elastic forces of the network acting in internal system, but they took into consideration the ion hydration and ion-pair formation between cation and resin formula with changed medium. This combined effect changed the activities of the ions and hence the equilibrium constants.

18. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 70, 1293; 1951, 73, 842.

19. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 493.

20. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1952, A214, 207.

21. *Ibid.*, 1953, A214, 344.

To us it appears that exchange, which depends on hydrated ionic sizes in aqueous solutions, is modified in non-aqueous solvents chiefly due to ion dehydration caused by increasing quantities of ethanol. This ion dehydration diminishes the sizes of the ions and hence there is enhanced exchange comparatively from ethanolic solutions. But one should not forget the swelling effect in ethanolic (or other non-aqueous) solvents. Swelled resins show enhanced exchange. In ethanolic solutions therefore the ion dehydration and swelling effects play their parts simultaneously, leading to net increase in exchange for any cation with increase in %EtOH. This explanation no doubt takes into consideration Wiegner's earlier idea of ion dehydration in alcoholic solutions, but also includes Gregor's concept. It is also not in contradiction to the basic consideration of Glueckauf²⁰ and Duncan²¹.

The change in the sequence of affinity of Ag^+ with respect to alkali metal ions and Li^+ can be explained in the following way. In aqueous solutions hydrated ions decide the sequence of affinity and thus the sequence for alkali metal ions is $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$. This sequence does not change in ethanolic solutions as the extent of dehydration caused by it must be nearly the same for these ions. The ionic radii for thallium (I) and silver ions are 1.49 and 1.26 respectively and hence z/r values (ratios of charge to ionic radius) for them would be 0.67 and 0.79 respectively. As the ions having low z/r ratios are hydrated less, thallium (I) ion will be less hydrated as compared to silver and potassium ($z/r=0.75$) ions. Its position therefore will always be after potassium in affinity sequence (ions being arranged in increasing order). Position of Ag^+ ion should be between sodium and potassium ions in affinity sequence in aqueous solutions in which the ions are hydrated to the greatest extent. But in dehydrated conditions also (i.e. in presence of EtOH) its position should be the same because the atomic radius of silver is 1.26 which is more than that of sodium (0.91) and less than that of potassium (1.33). Our results and plots of Fig. 1 show that though in ethanolic solutions this sequence is followed, it is not obeyed in aqueous solutions. In the latter, silver ion is exchanged more than potassium ion. The only reason that can be attributed to this unexpected behaviour of silver ion is that this ion is not hydrated so much as expected or the effect of ion-pair formation with the resin (as suggested by Glueckauf²⁰) might be playing its part together with the hydration effect.

Changes in sequences of affinity in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents have been shown by Wiegner⁵⁻⁶ from his studies on aluminosilicate exchangers. The recent studies⁹⁻¹², which have been performed on commercially available exchangers, do not, however, throw any light on such changes in affinity sequences of the ions having the same valency. The present studies show these changes very well from equilibrium studies on commercially available nuclear sulphonic acid type of exchanger in hydrogen form, using various types of univalent ions at different ionic concentrations, keeping the temperature and the resin quantity the same.